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The eponymous totem Swan in folk poems, epics, sagas, legends

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Resume. The article discusses the eponymous totem Swan (Kuv, Куу, Ку, Hu, Kyu, Kuo, Kugu), reflected in folk poems, epics, sagas, legends. Swan is one of the most ancient and romantic totems, personifying purity, beauty, grace, loyalty and collectivism. Totem Swan is a creation of prehistoric times, when primitive birth lived in harmony with nature and the wild animal world.

Keywords: eponym, totem, Swan (Kuv, Куу, Ку, Hu, Kyu, Kuo, Kugu), albiz, albus.

Эпоним-тотем Лебедь в народных поэмах, эпосах, сагах, легендах

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается эпоним-тотем Лебедь (Кув, Куу, Ку, Ху, Кыу, Куо, Кугу), отраженные в народных поэмах, эпосах, сагах, легендах. Лебедь как один из самых древних и романтических тотемов, олицетворяющий чистоту, красоту, грациозность, верность и коллективизм. Тотем Лебедь творение доисторического времени, когда первобытные роды жили в гармонии с природой и диким животным миром.

Ключевые слова: эпоним, тотем, Лебедь (Кув, Куу, Ку, Ху, Кыу, Куо, Кугу), albiz, albus.

Totem Swan. The eponymous-totemic concept of Swan (Kuv, Куу, Ку, Hu, Gu, Kyu, Kuo) is often found in folk epics and poems, ancient mythologies and legends, and their typological parallels can be traced. Apparently, the first totems appeared even in prehistoric times - then, when there was still childbirth, tribes lived in harmony with nature and the wild animal world. We agree with the opinion, where "in the "prehistoric period", the human body was more or less in a symbiotic relationship with the environment" [2, p. 191]. In ancient clans, tribes, the swan totem must have represented purity, beauty, grace, loyalty and collectivism. So, in Greek mythology, the wife of Paris, Elena the Beautiful, could turn into a swan. In the epic "Semetei", beautiful Aichurek flies in the guise of a swan, or in a Kazakh legend, a female swan saves Kalcha-batyr from a wound. According to the famous Soviet scientist, "the swan maiden is a fabulously mythological image dating back to remnants of the representations of the totemism period and is well known to the Turkic epos and folk traditions, as well as the tales of many other peoples" [12, p. 181].

In the poems of the Roman poet Lolli Bass (I century A.D.):

Let another turn into a bull

Or, having become a swan, he will sing a sweet song [1, p. 303]. Here we are talking about a thunderbolt: "In order to take possession of Danae, Europe and Leda, Zeus turned into golden rain, a bull and a swan, respectively" [1, p. 549]. Lucian of Samosata (II century A.D.): "... a hat in half an egg." A hint at the egg that Leda laid after she combined with Zeus, who took the form of Swans. From this egg were born Kastor and Pollux (Polydevk) -

Dioscuri. Children of Leda were also Elena and Clytemnestra" [15, p. 542].

"Totemic versions and ideas related to the emergence of the cult of a swan in the past were quite widespread among the Mongolian and Turkic tribes of the Altai region" [11, p. 12].

Screaming the carts of midnight

Lynx, swans of dissolution.

According to D. S. Likhachev, "in this last case another explanation is possible: swans could be a totem of the Polovtsy" [20, p. 17].

"The queen and her servant saw how tall warriors in high helmets decorated with swan wings landed on the shore.

"These are the Vikings, Herdis whispered" [21, p. 118]. It seems that the Vikings wore helmets with swan wings for a reason.

Walking Stick Grettir

Straight at the gates

To a friend of a blood swan

The arrows directed the fortress (Note: A friend of a blood swan is a warrior, i.e. a berserker (blood swan); p. 165) [17, p. 71]. It is noteworthy that according to the logic of commentators, the swan and berserker (wolf) have the same semantic basis.

From the legend of the justification of Kiev: "And there were three brothers - Kiy, Schek, and Horeb, and their sister Lybed" [14, p. 16]. Perhaps the name of sister Lybed is a totemic eponym. If this is plausible, then her brothers could be representatives of the Lybed totem. So, "the widest range of opinions in the interpretation of the etymology of the name Lybed. A. A. Potebnya and A. Preobrazhensky correlate it with the word "swan". M.

Fasmer connects the origin of the name Lybed with the Scandinavian proper name" [9, p. 230].

From the poem "Iliad":

Peace did not last long on the plain of Scamander.

Like wild swans, rushed in fluttering white robes

From distant Africa, black Ethiopians. Memnon led them,

Son of Dawn and Typhon, brother of Priam [10, p. 304]. Why exactly "like wild swans"? Or, "for the swan road," where in Old Icelandic kenning the sea is meant: "... there, over the sea, // he said, we will find, // for the swan road, // the king of the glorious, // but poor in servants!" [7, p. 38].

Such identical examples are not single. So, "... the forefather of the Turks came from the" possessions of So, which lay in the north of the country of the Huns. "One of his descendants, Izhini Nashidu, born of a she-wolf and gifted with supernatural qualities, had two wives: a daughter of the spirit of heaven and a daughter of the spirit of winter. From the first he had four sons, of whom one turned into a swan ... "The cited legend is placed in the Chinese" History of the Northern Wei Dynasty "(from 386 to 558), ... and we must assume that the legend is recorded between 535-558 probably, according to the Turkic envoys" [3, p. 101]. It is curious that a swan son was born from the son of a she-wolf. The main thing is that in the ancient Turkic folk tales, the global totems of the wolf and the swan go as related eponyms. Or, "Konstantin Porfirogenit writes: "The present Ungars ... the other part to the West and the Voivode (Ungars of Slavic named their leader) as their own, called Lebedia, settled in the places of Atelkusu and called them "Turks" [13, p. 128]. Here, Lebedia goes as an eponym, and they (Ungars) settled in the places of Atelkusu (perhaps on the land of Attila + Ku + su (su - possessive affix)).

Kuu (huu, kuv, guv, gu, kugu) is a swan.

In the epic "Semetei":

Dep oshentip Aychurok, (Having said so Aychurek,)

Akyly jandan tabylyp, (Thinking carefully,)

Ak kuu kebin zhamynyp, (Dressed up as a white swan)

Kanatyn kungo kakkilap ... (She waved her wings to the sun ...)

Aylanyp jurdu el tappay (I flew without finding anyone) [25, p. 151]. The main character of the epic "Semetei" (the second part of the epic "Manas") Aychurek (the future wife of Semetei (son of Manas)) could fly in the guise of a swan. The name Aichurek consists of two words: ay (moon) and churek (beauty), i.e. Lunar Beauty.

"So kugu is the swan. In modern languages, the name in the same form is preserved in Turkish - kugu; in other Turkic languages it underwent various phonetic transformations, for example: alt., kirg. kuu, kkalp. ak, hack. huu, kumyk kuv, turkm. guv, uzb. Kuv, Azerb. gu. Wed the Estonian name for the swan, which is also etymologized as onomatopoeic kuigas or Greek kyklos with the same meaning" [5, p. 13]. "With the name quw swan, the tribal name of the Altai people is the Kumandins; Wed also the name of another Altai tribe - Lebedins" [6, p. 68]. Apparently, in the great migration of the Huns, Scythian-Saks, Altai nationalities, this totem with them migrated to the expanses of Eastern and Central Europe.

According to M. Zakiev, "geese before their taming were ordinary migratory birds, and among a number of Turkic tribes the wild goose was a totem of a clan or tribe, representatives of which referred to themselves as kaz. This is confirmed by the existence of the Kyu tribe. In one of the Turkic dialects, kyu means "wild goose". There is a whole system of ethnonyms going back to this word: kyu keshe, kyuman (kyuban), kyumandy, kyuvar, kyuchak (kypchak)" [19, p. 38]. It is of interest here that in the Turkic-Polovtsian ethnonyms kyuman (kuman) and kyuchak (kypchak) there is an eponym-totem kyu. The ethnographer V.N. Tadykin's ethnographer has the same conclusions: "The presence of a nominal predicate with a predicate indicator: asmen (asman), Turk men (Turkman), ada men (ataman), Kumen (Kuhman), Bai Man (Mayman), As Kizhi (Askishi), etc." [22, p. 21]. In deciphering the token, Kuman, an ethnologist, was obviously right, it consists of two words: kuu and mans. Or, "... this ethnonym consists of three roots - lexemes: men + ku + ash (as) I am (a person) as from the Kuu tribe. "The ethnonym Türkic: Mongush is the basis of the anthroponym common among Altaians at the level of the surname (family) Menkushev" [22, p. 22]. What's important in the title is Mongush tribe has eponyms Kuu and Az. It seems to us that the eponym Man is part of the ethnonym Mongush.

In the Yakut epic: "Free from captivity // Light-faced Tuyaarym Kuo // Riding a pacific Gned // Your beautiful bride // Whose father is Sakha Saryn Toyon, // Whose mother is Sabyya Baai Khotun" [16, p. 169]. This is the blessing of the foremother Aan Alakhchyn ("Aan Alakhchyn Khotun from the sacred tree Aar-Luup", pp. 168-170) of the protagonist of the Yakut epic Nyurgun Uoalan. The name Alakhchyn is very reminiscent of the ethnic name Alakhchyn (Alchyn, Alshyn) [24, pp. 92, 223] Kazakhs and Kyrgyz. Such similarities would mean their identical ethnic basis. Apparently, the Yakut Aan Alakhchyn is an echo of the era of matriarchy. And, the light-faced Tuyaarym Kuo is the light-faced Tuyaarym Swan (Kuo). Therefore, the beautiful bride of the protagonist was connected with the Kuo totem, this could mean that in the Yakut ethnic associations there was such a well-known tribe.

According to M. Usmanov, the term huu in the modern Khakass language is used in the meanings: white, pale colorless; Huu-iney (Hat-iney) - this is the Khakass name of one of the characters of folk demonology, in which researchers see the image of a woman ancestor (cf. : in the archaic Khakass myth two human trees are declared ancestors - Umai and Ulgen). In any case, Huu-inei frost can be considered one of the editions of the image of the mother goddess, the ancestress of the same circle as Umai [18, p. 62]. It may well be that the Kuv primary totem (Kuu, Ku, Kyu) was formed from the image of the female ancestor Huu-inei.

In etymological dictionaries, in addition to different phonetically identical versions of it, there are other phonetic devices of the version, for example, "swan. Related Doctor of History albiz, elbiz "swan", ... lat. albus "white", Greek "White spot" [23, p. 470]. The explanations of the same nature are found in early linguistic works: "Swan: the word is pre-Slavic; to make him related to dr. ver. him. alpiz, ot albus" [8, p. 177]. It is noteworthy that in the words albus, albiz, alpiz is the word "white". By the way,

in the Turkic languages, the swan is ak kuw, ak ku, ak kuu (ak is white). If based on Greek, Latin. and doctor of historical sciences If these are the words “swan”, it seems

that there are two separate words in it, al (el,) and biz (bus). However, most importantly, these words indicate white color, i.e. ak (white), ak kuw (white swan).

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